

Electrical, mechanical and magnetic properties of organic-inorganic hybrid single crystal (ethylene diammoniumtetrachlorocobaltate(II) chloride)

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Abstract : Electrical, mechanical and magnetical properties of ethylene diammoniumtetrachlorocobaltate(II) chloride (EDACCo) single crystal prepared by slow evaporation method have been investigated. The resistivity measurement were carried out by using four probe method and it used to explain the electrical and electronic properties of the crystal. Band gap is also calculated from resistivity measurement. The variation of magnetic moment of the grown crystals under an applied static magnetic field was studied by Vibrational Sample Magnetometer (VSM). The room temperature magnetization results revealed a ferromagnetic behaviour for the EDACCo crystal. The mechanical properties of crystal were evaluated by mechanical testing which reveals certain mechanical characteristics. The Vickers hardness number (H_v) was found to increases with the increase in load and Meyer's index number ' n ' was calculated from H_v shows material falls in soft material category. Using Wooster's empirical relation, the elastic stiffness constant (C_{11}) has been calculated from Vickers hardness values.

Keywords : Room temperature ferromagnetism, mechanical properties, spintronics, electrical properties.

Introduction

Conventional electronics is based on inorganic materials because of their electric and magnetic properties. But the usage of these materials is constrained because of their expensive processing and their fabrication process. Mainly focused on spin-transport properties, due to potential device applications. Spintronics devices such as spin-valve transistors spin light-emitting diodes, non-volatile memory, logic devices, optical isolators and ultrafast optical switches are some of the parts of attention for introduction of ferromagnetic properties at room temperature in semiconductors¹. Organic materials were allowing with reasonable fabrication process. Moreover organic materials are flexible and their properties can be adjusted by making small changes in the chemical composition. Inorganic-organic hybrid materials combine the robustness of inorganics with the processability of organics². It is significant to examine deeply the association between the perovskite structure and functional properties of the hybrid compound, which is aorigin for design and growth of the materials with unique capabilities³. Chelating amine ligands form a variety of complexes with transition metal ions⁴. In recent years, great consideration has been paid to the complexation of ethylenediammine with many tran-

sition metals⁵. Smith and Stratton synthesized the title compound and examined the crystal structure of the complex by a Picker FACS-I diffractometer⁶.

Here, we investigate the electrical, mechanical and magnetic properties of EDACCo crystal and demonstrate that it exhibits room temperature ferromagnetism. Mechanical studies show that the material belongs to soft materials category.

Experimental

Synthesis :

Synthesis of organic-inorganic hybrid EDACCo crystal previously reported through self-assembly crystallization from an aqueous solution of ethylenediammine, $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and HCl, by slowly evaporating water at room temperature⁶. Crystals in the form of prismatic blue plates with dimension of few mm were obtained.

Results and discussion

Resistivity measurement :

Four probe methods can be used to determine the resistance of the single crystal. Here current passes through the outer contacts which are close to edges of the sample. The potential difference is measured across the inner con-

tacts. The method can eliminate the effects of contacts resistance between the sample and electrical contacts and therefore is most suitable for low and accurate resistance measurement⁷. The resistivity of the material is obtained from the formula,

$$\rho = 2\pi S (V/I) \quad (1)$$

where S is the distance between probes $S = 0.1875$, V is the obtained voltage across the inner contacts and I is the current passing through the sample. The band gap of the material is calculated from the relation,

$$E_g = 2.303 \times 2k \times \text{slope} \quad (2)$$

where k is Boltzmann constant. The applied current is 8 mA and the resistivity is measured from room temperature to 480 K. Fig. 1 shows that temperature dependence of resistivity and the resistance value decreases with temperature. The temperature dependent electrical resistance is very important tool to explain the nature of electric,

Fig. 1. (a) The temperature dependence of resistivity, (b) $\log \rho$ versus $1/T$.

electronic and magnetic properties of the material⁷. The band gap of the material is obtained from the slope of $\log \rho$ versus $1/T$ graph. These band gap values follow the expected periodic trend based on electro negativities of pnictogen elements⁸. According to proceeding theory, an insulator must have a large band gap, so that at room temperature the conduction band is partially empty and the valance band is practically filled and a semiconductor must have a narrower band gaps so that appreciable number of carriers are present in the valance and conduction bands at room temperature.

Mechanical studies :

The mechanical characterization of the EDACCo crystal was made by microhardness tester (Mututoyo MH 112, Japan) at room temperature. The grown crystal with uniform and smooth faces and free from imperfections was chosen for the static indentation tests. Now the selected face was indented gently by changing the loads for a dwell period of 10 s using Vickers indenter attached to an incident research microscope. The Vickers indented impressions were almost square in shape. The length of the two diagonals was measured by a calibrated micrometer attached to the eyepiece of the microscope after unloading. For each load, at least five well-defined impressions were taken and the average of all the diagonals (d) was considered. The Vickers hardness number (H_V) was calculated using the standard formula,

$$H_V = 1.8544 P/d^2 \quad (3)$$

where P is the applied load in kg and d is in mm and H_V is in kg/mm^2 .

Crack initiation and disintegration becomes significant beyond 100 g of the applied load. So hardness test could not be carried out above this load. From Wooster's empirical relation⁷,

$$C_{11} = H_V^{7/4} \quad (4)$$

Elastic stiffness constant (C_{11}) of EDACCo crystal was calculated. Fig. 2(a) shows the variant of H_V as a function of applied load range from 10 g to 100 g for the EDACCo crystal. It is very clear from the figure that H_V value increases with load increases. The Meyer's index number was calculated from the Meyer's law, which relates the load,

$$P = kd^n \quad (5)$$

$$\log P = \log k + n \log d \quad (6)$$

where k is material constant and n is the Meyer's index. In order to find the value of ' n ', a graph is plotted for $\log P$ against $\log d$ (Fig. 2(b)) which gives a straight line. From the slope of the line the Meyer's index number ' n ' was calculated to be 2.89. According to onitsch ' n ' should lie between 1 and 1.6 for harder materials and above 1.6 for softer materials. Thus EDACCo belongs to the soft material category⁸.

The resistance pressure is defined as a minimum level of depression load (W) below which there is no plastic

Fig. 2. (a) The variation of H_V as a function of applied load, (b) $\log P$ against $\log d$.

deformation. Hays and Kendall⁹ proposed an association to calculate the 'W' by the equation,

$$d^n = W/k_1 + (k_2/k_1) d^2 \quad (7)$$

The plot between d^n and d^2 gives a straight line (Fig. 3) having slope k_2/k_1 and intercept W/k_1 . From these values the value of W was calculated as 5.08 g. The elastic stiffness constant (C_{11}) was calculated using Wooster's empirical formula which gives an idea about the stiffness of bonding between neighbouring atoms.

Fig. 3. The plot between d^n and d^2 .

Magnetic studies :

Magnetic property of the crystal was studied using Vibrational Sample Magnetometer (VSM) Lakeshore VSM

7410. In VSM, the sample is made to vibrate sinusoidally in a constant field and the signal is induced to pickup coils yielding the magnetization curve. These magnetic domains are linked to reduction times and the magnetic properties of the material. The sample is estimated to respond well to magnetic field without any permanent magnetization at room temperature. Hysteresis behaviour (M-H) at room temperature is shown in Fig. 4, after deducting the linear diamagnetic background signal, the probable room temperature ferromagnetism was observed in sample with a saturation magnetization (M_s) of 0.0196 emu and the coercive field (H_c) of 397.14 G. The appearance of the ferromagnetic-like behavior is probably due to the presence of super paramagnetic metallic Co^{2+} ions within ligands.

Fig. 4. Hysteresis behaviour (M-H) of EDACCo crystal.

Conclusion

Electrical, mechanical and magnetical properties of ethylene diammoniumtetrachlorocobaltate(II) chloride (EDACCo) crystal have investigated. The temperature dependence of resistivity shows that the resistance value decreases with temperature and the activation energy was calculated to be 0.98 eV. Vickers hardness numbers were calculated for EDACCo crystal by the application of load and the hardness numbers were found to increase with increase in load. The value of the Meyer's index, n turned to be greater than 1.6 and thus EDACCo falls in the soft material category. The Vickers hardness versus load curve is in good agreement with the Hays and Kendall's theory of resistance pressure and the minimum load needed to

initiate the plastic deformations in the surface was calculated as 5.08 g. The VSM analysis shows that the crystal is belongs to room temperature ferromagnetic, this impiles that (EDACCo) compound has potential applications as spintronics in future.

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